

MODULAR TEACHING: EXPERIENCES OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12184522>

ABSTRACT

This qualitative study was conducted to further understand the junior high school teachers' experiences in teaching using modular teaching modalities. A modality that requires teachers' great efforts including its formulation, production, and implementation. Looking into the different experiences of teachers in their use of modular teaching modality may suggest certain realizations that may lead to further development in the teaching and learning process. This study aimed to explore the different experiences of junior high school public teachers in Catbalogan City in their use of the modular teaching modality. This study is determined to know the positive and the negative experiences of the teachers, describe their preparations employed, and their aspirations in improving the said modality. The study utilized sixteen (16) junior high school public teachers from the ten (10) district schools in Catbalogan City Division. The themes created were: *Teaching with a Heart, Learning Independently, Developing Family Link, Healthy Teaching, Motivated and Inspired, Deteriorating Motivation for Learning, Unprogressive Result for Learning, Risk-taking for the Sake of Learning, Earning over Learning, Losing Trust among Parents, Exhausting Resources for Learning, Reliability of Students Learning, All efforts are Exhausted for Learning, Modifying Teaching and Learning using Modules for Learning, Demanding yet Rewarding, Mens Sana in Corpore Sano (A Sound Mind in a Sound Body), The Commitment to Continuous Learning, Assurance of Human Interactive Modules, Empowering for Alternative Learning Modality, Innovating Quality Amidst Flexibility, Modules with a Heart for Learners' Well-being, Focusing Further on the Essential, and Flexing the Curriculum for Quality*. The findings and recommendations were used to further understand modular teaching modality. Moreover, the realizations taken from the experiences of the teacher-respondents suggest innovation in the

formulation, production, and implementation of modules which are vital to the said modality.

Keywords: *Modular Teaching Modality, New Normal Education, Learning Modules, Experiences of teachers, Aspirations of teachers*

INTRODUCTION

There has recently been a growing interest in developing learning modules for self-paced learning, which is essential and practical in the pandemic. Many pieces of evidence show that learners learn best when they do it themselves, focusing on a specific learning task and succeeding at it, as indicated in the educational principles. In designing modules, teachers must remember that it is a great privilege and, at the same time, a responsibility. It can be found to be problematic in the beginning when designing, especially when identifying where things should begin (Burge, 2019).

The necessity of using blended learning specifically on the use of modular distance learning has led many researchers to talk about different learning modules and their effectiveness for learning. These studies, however, have never addressed the issues and challenges experienced in crafting and implementing the use of learning modules. A few pieces of literature speak about these issues.

In the Philippines, the educational system has adapted the new blended learning, which includes the modular distance learning modality in all public schools in the country. In this modality, learners are expected to complete the tasks in the module, after which they have to submit their outputs at the end of the week. Moreover, Mean-Chin (2020) enumerated some of the disadvantages seen in the implementation of the said modality. This includes the availability of the materials. Considering the number of students, the budget available, and the equipment to use in crafting and implementing these modules, teachers may not have it all together, which consequently results in the lack of modules produced, hence the unavailability of materials.

Furthermore, there have been a lot of issues regarding the sense of authority, which focuses on the pressure of studying among learners. Consequently, the pressure of learning is greater for them in modular distance learning than it is during face-to-face or in an online class, considering that learning of topics is solely given to them and their teachers are too far away to offer them help. Aside from this, there are also issues of focus and concentration among learners; the confusion brought about by unclear and incomprehensible instructions; the confusion brought about by the different subjects; and the confusion with their situations at home. Most importantly, the question of the parent's or guardian's educational background is one that teachers and educational institutions are considering, not because they don't have the ability, but because they don't have the confidence to help their students. Thus, students are then again left on their own in

accomplishing their modules, usually seeking the help of their peers and taking refuge in the information found on the internet.

The need for exploration in this area is necessary for the educational system to make the necessary interventions in making it more effective. And looking into this through the perspective of the teachers, make it more reasonable, given that they are the craftsperson and implementer of modules. In the desire to become a part of this intervention and being one of the many teachers who is experiencing such an endeavor, the researcher made the necessary move to be part of it. The skills and competence in conducting the research study make the intervention more effective given that the necessary research design is applied, and coming up with an effective training design that is research-based will help those who are in the administrative position to develop, design, and implement an effective one.

Furthermore, although the primary goal of developing a learning module is to have successful self-paced learning among learners in this pandemic, we can never deny the persons behind the development of learning modules. Thus, this study aims to explore the experiences of junior high school teachers in Catbalogan City Division in the modular distance learning modality. Thus, this study assumes that there are significant experiences that can be identified as they adapt to the modular distance learning modality and can be used for necessary intervention for a more effective teaching and learning process.

Research Questions

This study explored the experiences of Junior High School Teachers in modular teaching modality, Catbalogan City Division, Catbalogan City, Samar, School Year 2021-2022:

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following queries:

1. What are the positive and negative experiences the informants encountered in modular teaching modality?
2. How would the informants describe their preparation in the modular learning modality?
3. What are the aspirations of informants to improve the modular teaching modality?

METHODOLOGY

This study is a qualitative research design employing the single case study design. A single case study is an in-depth investigation of a person, a group of people, or a unit to generalize across multiple units. An extensive, systematic analysis of a single individual, group, community, or other unit in which the researcher investigates in-depth data relating to multiple factors is also known as a case study. Furthermore, by outlining the actions followed while employing a case study technique, the researcher is able to narrow down a complicated and broad topic, or phenomenon, into a manageable research issue (s). The researcher acquires a more in-depth understanding of the

phenomenon by gathering qualitative and quantitative datasets about it than if they only used one sort of data (Heale and Twycross, 2017).

Moreover, it is a detailed examination of a single person, group, or event. A case study examines practically every aspect of a person's life and background to find patterns and reasons for their behavior. Also, it is useful in many domains, including psychology, medicine, education, anthropology, political science, and social work (Cherry, 2019).

The study was conducted in all public junior high schools in the Catbalogan City Division. There are a total of eight (8) public junior high schools under the ten (10) district schools of the division. The following schools are: Samar National School, Eastern Visayas Regional Science High School, Catbalogan City Agro-Industrial School, Guinsorongan National High School, Silanga National High School, Pangdan National High School, Antonio G. Tuazon National High School, Catbalogan National Comprehensive High School. All of the schools cater to students coming from the city and the neighboring municipalities.

The Samar National School (SNS) is the mother school of the province of Samar, formerly known as Samar High School. It is located on San Francisco Street, Catbalogan City, Samar. It consists of four thousand one hundred sixty-four (4,164) junior high school students. Presently, one hundred ninety-four (194) junior high school teachers serve at Samar National School.

The Eastern Visayas Regional Science High School is the only science high school in the division. It is located in San Roque, Catbalogan City, Samar along Arteche Boulevard. It consists of three hundred fourteen (314) junior high school students. There are fifteen (15) teachers serving the school.

The Catbalogan City Agro-Industrial School is located on the 9 hectares of city-owned agricultural property in Brgy. San Vicente, Catbalogan City, Samar. The school is a training institution for giving Catbaloganons, particularly youngsters, the information, skills, and attitudes necessary to become producers and/or agripreneurs in response to the city government's food security and greening projects. The school is composed of one hundred fifty-eight (158) students and five (5) teachers.

The Guinsorongan National High School is located in Brgy. Guinsorongan, Catbalogan City, Samar formerly known as Guinsorongan Integrated High School. It has six hundred seventy-one (671) junior high school students with twenty-nine (29) teachers serving them.

The Silanga National High School is located in Brgy. Silanga, Catbalogan City, Samar. It is composed of one thousand four hundred twenty-six (1,426) junior high school students and fifty-seven (57) teachers.

The Pangdan National High School is situated on a hilly portion of Brgy.Pangdan, 8 kilometers away from the city. It consists of three hundred and six (306) junior high school students with sixteen (16) teachers.

The Antonio G. Tuazon National High School is the only secondary school in the Sierra Islands, located between Barangay Rama and Barangay Cinco in Catbalogan City, Samar. It consists of six hundred eleven (611) junior high school students with twenty-four (24) teachers serving them.

The Catbalogan National Comprehensive High School, formerly known as the Samar Regional School of Fisheries, is located in Brgy. Mercedes, Catbalogan City, Samar. It consists of one thousand two hundred four (1,204) junior high school students with fifty-two (52) teachers serving them.

To successfully come up with a centralized and effective gathering of narratives, participants in the study must have the following characteristics:(1) must be a legitimate faculty member or teacher at the institution; (2) must hold a teacher III or Master teaching position; and (3) must have experience crafting modules in the division.

There were sixteen (16) informants for this study. Eight of these informants were utilized for the Individual Interview (IDI) and eight informants for the Focus Group Discussion (FGD). There was one (1) informant from each of the eight (8) public junior high schools in the division who was utilized for the Individual Interview (IDI) and an additional (1) informant from each of the eight (8) public junior high schools was utilized for the Focus Group Discussion (FGD).

The research instrument that was used in the conduct of the study is the researcher-made interview questionnaire. The instrument was used to gather the needed data and ideas from the target informants. The research instrument contained open-ended questions which were answered by the informants. The open-ended questions determined the common patterns or themes of the answers that were provided by the informants. The answers to the open-ended questions were verified through focus group discussion. The research instrument was checked by experts. The purpose of this is to determine the reliability and validity of the instrument in collecting the desired information, time allocation to answer the questionnaire and format and sequencing of the questions.

There was an approval letter in the conduct of the data gathering given to different schools and the Schools Division Superintendent. The adviser has approved this letter from the researcher before distribution. Upon approval of the letter, the respondents were chosen from among the faculty members using the inclusion criteria presented and approved by the adviser. Subsequently, the researcher asked the respondents for a scheduled individual interview and a focused group discussion (FGD), with consideration to a particular health protocol and with much consideration to their availability. Moreover, ethical considerations were read and explained to the respondents to highlight the confidentiality of the interview.

The data collection process was conducted through an individual interview and a focused group discussion. Individual interviews were done in person over the months of October and November 2021, lasting around half an hour each or an average of 27.75 minutes, to elicit relevant experiences from the informants. The interview schedule was set accordingly. Moreover, FGD was conducted on November 19, 2021 at 4:10 in the afternoon and lasted for forty-five minutes through an in-person discussion. This discussion was conducted for an in-depth validation of the data gathered. The data was recorded using notes and audio recordings, which were then analyzed.

In the data analysis, the researcher utilized the phenomenological data analysis by Colaizzi, employing the following steps.

First, the transcripts were read several times to gain a sense of the full content. This stage adds the respondents' thoughts, feelings, and ideas to the bracketing diary. This helped to explore the phenomenon experienced by themselves.

Second, the respondents' significant statements were noted in each transcript. These statements were written on separate sheets and coded based on their transcript, page, and line numbers.

Third, at this stage, the collected statements were given significant meaning. Subsequently, the underlying meanings of each statement were coded into one category as they are reflected in the detailed description.

Fourth, after having an agreement towards all formulated meanings, grouping and acquired implications were taken from each category to reflect the themes' unique structure. Each cluster of the theme was in a code to include all formulated meanings related to that group of definitions. After that, groups of clustered themes were under code to have all acquired implications related to that group of purposes. After that, groups of clusters of themes that reflect a particular vision issue were incorporated together to form a distinctive construct of themes. Indeed, all these themes are internally convergent and externally divergent, meaning that each formulated meaning falls only in one theme cluster that is unique from other structures (Mason, 2002).

Fifth, the themes were arranged into a detailed description at this analysis stage. After merging all the pieces, the whole structure of the phenomenon was coded and noted, then an expert was asked to review on the findings in terms of richness and completeness to provide sufficient and detailed descriptions. Finally, the results were presented to the adviser for thorough explanation.

Sixth, this step is similar to the previous step, but there are no specific meanings involved. In this step, the reduction of findings was redundant, and eradicating misused or overestimated descriptions from the overall structure is repetitive. Hence, this endeavor was meant to emphasize the fundamental design. Some amendments were made to apply to generate transparent relationships between theme clusters and their extracted

themes, which includes eliminating some ambiguous structures that weaken the description.

Seventh, this step aimed to validate the study findings using the checking technique. The researcher got approval from the participants in advance for the conduct of the study.

RESULTS

This qualitative study used a thorough understanding of the transcribed responses of each key informant by reading and re-reading the transcripts to determine the general sense of the whole coverage of its content. The significant statements from the transcript of the interview and focus group discussions were extracted, recorded, and coded using Excel and manual coding. The significant statements were properly coded, noting the informant number and the response number for easy tracking.

There was a total of one hundred eighty-one (181) significant statements that reflected the positive and negative experiences of the informants in modular education in teaching in the new normal as well as the aspiration of the informants to improve modular education in teaching in the new normal.

From the one hundred eighty-one (181) significant statements extracted from the transcripts, the researcher developed Formulated Meanings from the significant statements gathered. There were one hundred twelve (112) Formulated Meanings developed from the significant statements. Of the one hundred twelve (112) Formulated Meanings, there were twenty-three (23) clustered themes and three (3) Emergent Themes. The emergent themes and Theme Clustered are as follows:

- I. Positive and Negative Experiences in Modular Teaching Modality**
 - A. Positive Experiences the Informants Encountered in Modular Teaching Modality**
 1. Teaching with a Heart
 2. Learning Independently
 3. Developing Family Link
 4. Healthy Teaching
 5. Motivated and Inspired
 - B. Negative Experiences the Informants Encountered in Modular Teaching Modality**
 1. Deteriorating Motivation for Learning
 2. Unprogressive Result for Learning
 3. Risk-taking for the Sake of Learning
 4. Earning Over Learning
 5. Losing Trust among Parents
 6. Exhausting Resources for Learning

7. Undependable Students Learning

II. Descriptions of the Informants in the Preparation in Modular Teaching Modality

1. All Efforts are Exhausted for Learning
2. Modifying Teaching and Learning Using Modules for Learning
3. Demanding yet Rewarding
4. Mens Sana in Corpore Sano (A Sound Mind in a Sound Body)

III. Aspirations of the Informants in Improving the Modular Teaching Modality

1. The Commitment for Continuous Learning
2. Assurance of Human Interactive Modules
3. Empowering for Alternative Learning Modality
4. Innovating Quality Amidst Flexibility
5. Modules with a Heart for Learners' Well-being
6. Focusing Further on the Essential
7. Flexing the Curriculum for Quality Education

The emergent themes that were created were developed to describe the phenomenological narratives to describe the answers to the problem statement identified. The three (3) emerging themes with different theme clusters each are discussed below.

I. Positive and Negative Experiences in Modular Teaching Modality

A. Positive Experiences the Informants Encountered in Modular Teaching Modality

1. Teaching with a Heart. The theme that was developed from the phenomenological narratives expressed by the informants leads to a deeper meaning of teaching in this modular learning modality giving a chance of knowing learners better.

During the one-on-one interview, Informants 1 and 3 expressed their positive experience in the modular learning modality. They said:

I have known my students better and acknowledge their weaknesses, background, and status (IDI 3-1).

I was able to know my students very well, their status at home and the struggles that they are facing (IDI 1-1).

Knowing better my students not just merely their names but their lives at home (IDI 1-1.2).

In addition, six (6) Informants in the FGD expressed the same sentiments that were felt by the informants in the one-on-one interview. They expressed:

I have more time to study my topic and deliver it more accurately to the students (FGDI 1-1).

I have learned and explored other ways of teaching aside from the usual face-to-face classes. Aside from that, I have also allotted more time in monitoring students which I seldom do during the normal set-up (FGDI 1-1.2).

Getting to know better the background and personality of our learners is a positive experience for me (FGD1 4-1.2).

There is a realization that we need to be considerate to our students for every learner have their own struggles in life (FGDI 5-1).

Teachers became more creative and resourceful. With less resources we can be able to provide education to the students (FGDI 6-1).

Teachers were made to think out of the box and be creative to still ensure the delivery of quality education despite the challenges of the pandemic (FGDI 6-1.2).

The distribution and retrieval of modules, as well as providing guidance on how to use the modules, have been great experiences for me (FGDI 7-1).

2. Learning Independently. The said theme is derived from the responses of the informants describing the effect of modular learning among learners which can be considered a good sign for the process of learning.

Informants 2 and 5 during the one-on-one interview expressed how the modular mode of learning affected the performance of the learners. They mentioned:

They were able to become more independent in terms of comprehension, but the different lessons and at the same time working on several tasks both for every learning area and also managing their skills in time management to comply with needed outputs for a particular week, thus grooming them to be very flexible individuals (IDI 2-1.2).

I find it helpful on the part of the students because they will be knowledgeable on the different subjects while they are at home and safe to be infected by the virus. With this, they developed a kind of bond with their parents and guardians while answering the module (IDI 5-1).

When I checked my student's output. Their creativity is so amazing. Despite the fact that the teacher is not around physically to guide them at home, still they manage to expand their horizons. With this, I can say that they are learning (IDI 5-1.2).

Moreover, this was also supported by informant 5 in the FGD. The informant said:

It helps students to hone their time management. Children are safe from the pandemic for they are not allowed to go outside unless they are vaccinated (FGDI 5-1).

3. Developing Family Link. The theme is derived from the responses of the informants, expressing how the learning modules developed the link between family members, most of whom are parents making time to teach their children.

Seven (7) of the informants shared their experiences with the support and the link development of the families. They said:

There is a strong collaboration and partnership between the teachers and parents to make this distance learning a success. Parents reinforce the students at home. They also contact me to ask about the topic which is complex especially in my subject, Math (IDI 2-1.2).

Parents collaborate with me as a teacher in the learning process. I tutor the parent in school and the parent will tutor her child at home. The parents are happy to share to their children the learnings they gained from me as their child's teacher (IDI 5-1.2).

Its optimism is exemplified by parents who are never weary of picking up and returning school modules (IDI 6-1).

I can personally have a conversation with the parents/ guardians since I do the home visitation or monitoring (IDI 6-1.2).

We had a chance to talk to our learners and parents and we see their situation (IDI 8-1).

This sort of pedagogy encourages teacher-parent collaboration and partnership. Parents are already visible, and we can always talk about how to improve a child's performance or how to urge and inspire their child or children to accomplish more and be more in spite of their circumstances (IDI 7-1.2).

Teachers have not stressed-out disciplining directly the learners because they are at home. It is their parents or guardians who discipline them, remind them about the things to accomplish especially the deadlines of the modules and other learning tasks. In this situation, the parents can bond with their children. They can also tutor their children about the lesson intended for a particular week (IDI 7-1).

In addition, three (3) of the informants in the FGD expressed the same observation during visitation and follow-up of modular learning of the learners. They expressed:

I had been learning continues and the willingness to accept change. Learning continues with the shared responsibilities with the parents who guided and tutored their children at home. Learners also value and learn how to manage time effectively (FGDI 2-1).

It allows parents to tutor their kids at home and identify their kids' strengths as well as areas in which they are weak or unable to understand. This is their bonding moment also (FGD1 7-1.2).

On how to teach the lesson or topic at home, parents and guardians collaborate with us, the teachers. We collaborate for the benefit of the student. They also provided their children more time because some of them had lost work due to the pandemic (FGD1 8-1).

4. Healthy Teaching. The theme that has been developed comes from the phenomenological narratives expressed by the informants, expressing how light the process of teaching and learning is today in this pandemic because there are informants who see it as an avenue to stay healthy amidst the pandemic.

Four (4) informants mentioned how the pandemic has helped them improve their health. They mentioned:

I am not under as much time pressure in class, and less stress in terms of classroom management and discipline since no students are in the classroom but honestly speaking, I miss their noise and presence (IDI 3-1.2)

Teachers became more open-minded and more patient considering the delays of the materials needed in printing the modules. There is no room for "me" but "we" as us teachers in this school helped one another in printing, and sorting the modules just to meet the deadline and the schedule of the distribution of the modules (IDI 4-1.2).

I was able to reinvent myself and adjust to the circumstances as a result of these experiences (IDI 6-1).

The education system today, helps me to relax my vocal cords especially that I have a thyroid problem (IDI 8-1).

5.Motivated and Inspired. The theme generated from the phenomenological narratives expressed by the informants expresses the brighter side of the pandemic, where even if modular learning is quite demanding they can find the light of motivation and inspiration along with the modular learning modality.

Informant 4 expressed during the one-on-one interview the motivation for teaching despite the challenge of the pandemic. The informant mentioned:

I was able to teach despite this pandemic and education continues. Limited interaction during monitoring or distribution of modules but it is worth it. The fact that I can see their smiles holding and reading the contents of the module made me feel happy (IDI 4-1).

Seeing the students' real-life situations at home motivated me to strive harder. Despite living in an uncomfortable house and facing financial difficulties, they were able to continue their studies through this modality. Regular student monitoring serves as a wake-up call to all teachers to continue working with compassion and empathy (FGDI 8-1.2).

I can personally visit the learners and I can see the real situation of the learners at home. Some of them are really struggling financially and economically. The situation at home is very poor. Then I came to realize that there is a really a purpose of the monitoring and having this kind of learning modality (FGD1 4-1).

B. Negative Experiences the Informants Encountered in Modular Teaching Modality

1.Deteriorating Motivation for Learning. The theme that was generated from the narratives given by the informants expressed the opposite of the light of motivation and inspiration because some informants have deteriorating motivation for learning due to the other side of the modular learning modality.

Five (5) of the informants in the one-on-one interview expressed how their motivation deteriorated. They said:

I am saddened with the fact that despite of the teachers' efforts in printing the modules, sleeping late at night, and everything, some students does not care. They failed to comply the activities stated in the module (IDI 1-1).

There are some learners who encounters difficulty in understanding and completing these outputs for the lessons at hand resulting to non-submission of the completed module or submitting it without answers (IDI 2-1.4).

It is quite stressful preparing the modules for the students especially if you have a large number of students (IDI 3-1.4).

The returned modules, on the other hand, are either incomplete or contain no responses. It tainted the entire experience (IDI 6-1).

With this type of modality, there is no guarantee that the students are actually learning (IDI 7-1).

The five (5) informants' narrative during the one-on-one interview was supported also by Informants 2 and 3 during the FGD interview. They said:

The most challenging part as a teacher while on modular teaching modality is how I could help my students to comprehend well on the lessons reflected on the modules (FGDI 2-1.4).

The learner the way I see it cannot grasp the totality of the concept (FGDI 3-1.4).

2.Unprogressive Result for Learning. The theme was derived from the narratives of the informants expressing their frustration relative to the negative effect of the modular learning modality on the progress of students' learning in this pandemic.

Nine (9) of the informants expressed in their narrative the negative effect of the modular learning among learners. They said:

I found out that some of the learners really needs help from the teachers not only to develop their knowledge, but rather how to understand their situation, you know their... family background (IDI 1-1).

They rather not answer those things because they don't understand the content of the module especially in Math, Science, and English subjects (IDI 1-1).

The activities on the module shall really suit the needs and interests of the students because no two individuals are alike. Some of the activities are too hard for the learners to understand. Slow learners cannot easily grasp the content of the modules since it is standard and suited for fast learners. It is frustrating on the part of the slow learners especially when they have no parent or somebody at home to act as a tutor (IDI 4-3.2).

Some of my students cannot understand the content of the modules, especially in AP modules (IDI 6-1.4).

The challenge here is how to handle the 'SLOW LEARNERS' they can read but they cannot comprehend well... sometimes I allowed them to answer the modules in Waray- Waray language for them to express their thoughts and ideas (IDI 6-1.4).

There are learners who submitted their activities or answer sheets incomplete or no answer at all (IDI 8-1.4).

There are submitted activities/ answer sheet with no names and it is difficult for me to guess and check who is the owner of those submitted activities (IDI 8-1.4).

In addition, three (3) of the informants in the FGD shared the same sentiments with what the nine (9) other informants during the one-on-one interview. The FGD informants said:

Ensuring that students learn with the use of modules/LAS only, reaching out students who live on far flung barangays and municipalities, giving remediation to students especially those who got low scores in tests, printing of modules and other additional tasks such as distribution and retrieval of modules and output (FGDI 1-1.4).

There is a lack of social interaction between the teacher and students. Students didn't understand much what is in the module for some topics are hard to understand without further explanations (FGDI 5-1).

Challenges in printing the modules, challenges in writing the modules, challenges also in the delivery because the modular delivery hindered the 'teacher's touch' (FGDI 6-1.4).

The printing and sorting of modules are the drawbacks. It is not simple for teachers. Teachers cannot directly explain to the students; instead, parents do it. But because some of them lack education, parents cannot explain well the topic (FGDI 7-1).

Students who are having trouble understanding the lessons, particularly in Math, English, and Science. They are overburdened by the module's many activities. Some

students have already considered dropping out because they are too exhausted to complete the modules (FGDI 8-1.4).

3.Risk-taking for the Sake of Learning. The themes that were generated from the responses of the informants sharing the risks made by informants to continue the learning process.

The delivery of modules to the learners it is quite risky (IDI 2-1.4).

I feel bad knowing that the schedule of the distribution was not followed correctly (IDI 3-1).

The fare is expensive and aside from the fact that it is too dangerous for me to travel because I might be infected with the virus but I have no choice (IDI 5-1.4).

This was also supported by the informant during the FGD relative to the risks taken by the informants for continuous learning:

The delivery of the modules also we encounter delays. Time management is a challenge also (FGD1 4-1).

4.Earning over Learning. The theme generated from the narratives stated by the informants expresses the frustration of the informants towards some learners who choose to earn rather than invest in their academic performance.

With this frustration, informant shared the sentiments during the one-on-one interview supported with the narratives of informants from the FGD. They said:

They lack answers or performance tasks in my subject because they also lack resources at home and even hard to feed their hungry stomachs (IDI 3-1).

There is an instance that I came to my students' house and they are not around for they went to fishing. This is also one of the reasons why they cannot submit the modules on time because they prioritized fishing and other work to earn a living (IDI 4-1.4).

There are students who get their modules late than the given schedule (IDI 8-1.4).

During monitoring, some learners are not in their homes (IDI 8-1.4).

There are learners who are not at home during the scheduled monitoring because they are doing a job such as fishing, house helpers, and other child labor things (FGD1 4-1).

Students to be monitored were not around for they are doing some errands like plowing the field to support their daily needs. It made me feel bad (FGD1 6-1).

The risk and distance in the monitoring of students is one of the challenges. There is an instance wherein the dog is about to bite me. It really scares me. Rain or shine monitoring is a threat to my health. But I have to keep doing it because my students need me (FGD1 8-1.4).

5.Losing Trust among Parents. The theme-driven responses of the informants expressed another negative aspect seen in the modular learning modality, which is the participation of parents in the academic performance of their children and the demotivation brought by less cooperation.

From the one-on-one interview conducted it was clearly expressed by informants as to the behavior and actions done by parents. They said:

Some parents or guardians do not get the modules on the scheduled date and time, thus delaying the process. As a result, the completed modules will be returned late also (IDI 1-1.4).

Parents who fail to assist and give support to students, procrastination of students, mental health problems, late distribution and retrieval of modules, complex content on the modules, to name a few (IDI 1-3.1).

Despite various announcements and communications through text or messenger regarding the schedule of the distribution of modules, many of the students and parents do not even care. They shall wait that the said modules will be delivered to their respective homes (IDI 4-1).

When parents or guardians don't go to school on the schedule given to get the modules of their children (IDI 5-1.4).

The said experience was seconded by those informants from the FGD. They said:

Not all parents have the ability to teach their children, and other parents, and some of them also lacks time to do so since they are too busy working to provide for their children's fundamental needs (FGD1 7-1.4).

Some parents are unable to effectively teach at home because some of the topics are unfamiliar to them and difficult for them to comprehend due to their poor knowledge (FGD1 8-1).

6.Exhausting Resources for Learning. The theme driven from the narrative expressed by informants described another negative impact of the modular learning modality on the informants where they have insufficient materials for the production of modules.

There were seven (7) informants during the one-on-one interview expressed a narrative response that developed the theme. They said:

There are delays in the printing of the modules because of technical problems. Sometimes the printer is not working because of the volumes of prints produced (IDI 1-1.4).

Well, sometimes we run out of papers, ink, couple with a malfunctioning printer. The delays are intolerable (IDI 2-1.4).

There are more expenses and time consumed in the production and reproduction of modules. I even use my personal equipment and money just to meet the deadline and schedule of the distribution of learning materials (IDI 7-1).

I have difficulties retrieving the necessary output. I have to go to the students' house to check what is the reason for the delays. I have 30 advisees and it is difficult for me to reach them due to some clerical work to do. The number that they wrote on the enrollment form is not reachable also (IDI 7-1.4).

Teachers have so much paperwork mandated by DepEd. Instead of focusing on the preparation of learning materials, our time is consumed by the urgent deadlines of the documents needed (IDI 8-1.4).

Because of paper works or clerical works, checking of learners' output is too limited (IDI 8-1.4).

It takes time in printing of modules. Sometimes, printers are not working well because of over usage. It is hard to reproduce modules due to scarcity of bond paper and ink (IDI 8-1.4).

Moreover, Informants 1 and 7 in the FGD conducted share narratives with their experiences relative to this.

While the negative experience that I had in modular teaching is it is more tiring because teachers are bombarded with more paper works (FGDI 1-1).

It's also difficult to manage our limited time because we're constantly besieged with heaps of paper work, all of which is urgent. All I can do is just sigh (FGDI 7-1.4).

7.Undependable Students Learning. The theme is driven by the narrative responses describing their experience with the learner's learning authenticity and reliability.

Assessment and intervention are delayed since they return the modules after a week or longer, you know... ahmmm not all are religiously and taking the modular distance learning seriously (IDI 1-1.4).

The results of the assessment are not that credible anymore especially on the students' answers on the modules (IDI 1-1.4).

We give recognition to top students in Grade 10 but how can we be sure if the said student is really the person completing and answering the modules and performance tasks? See, the learning output is a question and I as a teacher is quite doubtful on that (IDI 2-1.4).

We cannot immediately provide immediate feedback to the students' performance. It takes time to provide feedback since I have to wait for the modules to be submitted to me (IDI 3-1.4).

Another challenge is checking if the students really answer the module. I have doubts that some of my students let somebody answer the module (IDI 5-1.4).

It is also a challenge checking the modules with no answer or parents returning the module without checking if it has answers or not (IDI 5-1.4).

The students are not performing well on their learning tasks. They submit a poor-quality product that does not adhere to the rubrics and requirements. They have this ingrained view that submitting an output, regardless of quality, is preferable than not submitting at all (IDI 7-1).

It is difficult to validate learners' performance because since there are some who have tutors, while some do not learn by themselves. Because of this system, you will not know, if the student/learner is really learning or just submitting the modules for grades specially so that at the last page of the modules, there are answers key (IDI 8-1.4).

Learners do not answer their modules seriously. Parents are the ones who answer the modules instead of the students and students tend to copy the answers of their classmates to the activities in the modules. They don't read the modules. They prefer to call a friend and ask for answers (FGD1 2-1).

Another challenge pose by the distance learning modality specifically on the modular teaching modality is the authenticity of the assessment. Although teachers are monitoring the learners at a regular basis at the back of the door, teachers are not so sure who answers some of these tests given to learners (FGDI 3-1.4).

Assessing the student is also a challenge because some of the activities are answered by the parents or tutors (FGD1 8-1.4).

II. Descriptions of the Informants in the Preparation in Modular Teaching Modality

1. All Efforts are Exhausted for Learning. The theme describes how, through the manifested effort, learning continues despite the challenge of the pandemic. When the researcher inquired, there were six (6) informants on one-on-one interview shared about their experiences on the exhausting preparation of the modules, they confided:

Well, it's not new to all that the preparation in the modular teaching modality is quite tedious. (IDI 1-2).

The preparation demands the completeness of materials-bond paper, printer, ink, manpower, and etc. (IDI 3-2.2).

I see to it that the printer is working, with ink, and I have an adequate supply of bond papers so that there will be no delays during the printing. I also prepare some learning activity sheets and summative test questionnaires for the students to assess the level of knowledge and understanding they gained (IDI 5-2.1).

The preparation is time-consuming considering the number of pages to be printed and we only have limited resources like a printer. Though this is our job sometimes it is exhausting also and it saddened me to know that we have bashers because they are telling us that we are not doing a lot of work or not working and yet we receive a salary (IDI 4-2.2).

It takes a lot of effort to get everything ready. You need a lot of energy, time, and patience considering the volume of pages to be printed, students to be monitored, parents to deal with, etc. (IDI 7-2).

It is tiring but we have to follow what is being mandated to us (IDI 8-2.2).

Moreover, informants from the FGD added how they describe the preparation of the learning modules. They said:

Preparation in modular teaching modality is very tedious and difficult especially because of lack of resources such as printers, bond papers, etc. (FGDI 1-2).

The delivery of the modules is also a challenge. It is an added cost for we have to hire a banca to deliver those modules (FGDI 4-1.4).

All of these preparations are very time and energy-consuming because I spend almost 3 days just for printing alone (FGDI 1-2.2).

I download the modules, print, sort and distribute the modules. I sometimes deliver it to the students' respective homes for some of the parents do not get it from school (FGDI 7-2.1).

Internet connectivity since we are located in an island barangay. It is difficult for us to download the materials. We have to wait for Friday or Saturday to download everything (FGDI 4-1.4).

Time is a challenge too. We have limited time because printing alone takes much of our time (FGDI 4-1.4).

Reaching out to the learners with no cellphone or messenger account is also a challenge. What we did in the school is that the classmate with phones or messenger accounts will be the one to relay the message (FGDI 4-1.4).

2.Modifying Teaching and Learning Using Modules for Learning. The theme-driven describes the ways made by the informants to modify the teaching and learning with the use of the modules. This also gives an avenue where the informants become the innovators in order to make the teaching and learning process simpler and more understandable as they prepare the learning modules.

Informants 1, 2, and 3 during the one-on-one interview expressed that aside from the usual routine that they are doing, they also prepare materials that would reinforce the Learning Modules. They said:

I download the module, print it, segregate, and inform the parents to get it in school. I also contextualize the downloaded module for easy understanding of the students (IDI 1-2.1).

I also prepare Learning Activity Sheets as required following the Most Essential Learning Competencies. I also prepare materials that I will use during the monitoring or home visitation (IDI 1-2.1).

We have to download the SLM then we have to print them, then design additional tasks or exercises for enhancement and remediation for the lessons (IDI 2-2.1).

I download and print the modules. Segregate it and distribute it to the students whether through his parents or deliver it at home. I also prepare Learning Activity Sheets for remediation and enrichment activities (IDI 3-2.1).

Six (6) informants of the FGD seconded of the efforts being done in simplifying and reinforcing the learning of learners through the use of the modules. They added:

I prepare Work Home Learning Plan, learning activity sheets, gather soft copy of learning activity sheets, sort them and prepare for the distribution (FGDI 1-2.1).

I study the MELC or the Most essential learning competencies. Prepare the Weekly Home Learning Plan together with the Learning Activity Sheets, prepare, sort, and distribute modules (FGDI 2-2.1).

I prepare a weekly home learning plan, learning activity sheets, summative tests and of course print, sort, and distribute modules (FGDI 4-2.1).

A combination of trial-and-error mechanism that up to now it is still subject for perfection. Printers sometimes doesn't work. My body and mind need relaxation but because of so much work to do, coordinator ship, and all I can't (FGDI 6-2).

I also prepare a weekly home learning plan and activity sheets based on the MELCs (FGDI 7-2.1).

I download the modules, print, sort, and distribute it. I prepare weekly home learning plan. Learning activity sheets and the monitoring schedule (FGDI 8-2.1).

3.Demanding yet rewarding. The developed theme describes the demands that the modules require, which becomes for them a rewarding task. Along the way of the development of learning modules, informants mentioned the challenging tasks of doing

modules, but seeing the appreciation expressed by parents and learners, the feeling of exhaustion is carefully paid off.

In the one-on-one interview with the informants, Informants 3, 5 and 6 mentioned:

I can say that the preparation is quite exciting now. Yes, it is tedious and requires a lot of time and energy but seeing the students and parents appreciate your efforts is a good feeling (IDI 3-2).

The preparation is both exhausting and rewarding. It is exhausting since there are numerous pages per subject to print, and it is rewarding when I see all of the modules stapled, piled, and ready for release (IDI 5-2).

We have so many clerical works and it demands so much of our time (IDI 6-2.2).

On the contrary, Informants 4 and 8 in the FGD expressed the challenges of the preparation of modules. They said:

Assessing students is also a challenge. Authenticity of the result is a big question (FGD1 4-1.4).

The preparation is challenging (FGDI 8-2).

4.Mens Sana in Corpore Sano (A Sound Mind in a Sound Body). The quest for continuous learning in this pandemic has been challenging among the informants because they have to consider their health conditions, which will affect the effectiveness of learning in a way that is structured and planned in a learning condition just like in this pandemic.

Informants 4 and 7 expressed that the time that the pandemic caused an avenue for physical health restoration and adjustment for another mode of learning. They expressed:

I also prepare myself to be physically healthy (FGDI 4-2.1).

Challenging compared to face-to-face instruction and still adjusting on the situation (FGDI 7-2).

The emergent and clustered themes transpired from the phenomenological narratives expressed by the informants showed how they describe the preparation of the learning modules used in this time of pandemic.

III. Aspirations of the Informants in Improving the Modular Teaching modality

1. The Commitment to Continuous Learning. The theme is driven by the narratives given by the informants describing their commitment to continue learning through the use of learning modules.

There were three (3) informants that expressed their experiences and commitment to continue learning amidst the pandemic. They said:

Since it's our job we have to, and we have to double our effort. Just for the students to have this quality of education (IDI 1-2).

The preparations are self-fulfilling and gratifying knowing that despite the pandemic learning continues (IDI 1-2.2).

I also aspire for more supportive parents and guardians who will really support, guide, and collaborate with the teachers for a common goal (IDI 4-3).

2. Assurance of Human Interactive Modules. The theme is driven by the narratives given by the informants to describe the need for adjusting the modules for learners to have a sound understanding of the modules where they can interact through the answers expressed in their modules.

Informants 2 and 7 during the one-on-one interview expressed by saying:

The learning materials were one of the things I wanted to improve in modular distance teaching modality (IDI 2-3).

Every school must be supported and adequately funded because we run out of resources and it causes headaches and stress to the teachers (IDI 7-3).

Moreover, six (6) of the informants shared the same with the previous informants during the FGD. They said:

Choose materials, objective and content of modules that is relative to the students' real-life experiences. Incorporate mindfulness. Always get connected to the parents to monitor the students (FGD1 5-3.2).

The implementation of modular teaching modality gives great adjustment to teachers and learners. On the point of improving the modality. I would like to mention about the SLM write up where there are a number of errors on the modules. These must be corrected during home visitations and interventions must be done directly telling the learners about these productions (FGD1 3-3).

Reduced module activities, more examples for each subject, weekly home visits, limited face-to-face classes or Blended Learning, provision of colored printed modules, immediate information from teachers on what to answer in the modules, and teachers' leniency in the submission of students' outputs are all things that should be done to improve the modular teaching modality (FGD1 4-3.2).

Limited face-to-face instruction is what I aspire for. Modular teaching alone cannot suffice what the learners really need. Also, a unified modular textbook. No more printing because it is a waste of time. In this way, I or we can focus more with the teaching and learning rather than printing and sorting (FGD1 6-3).

The school/department should make mechanisms on how the teacher will incorporate teacher's touch and learner's feel even if through a modular delivery. Blended modality is still the ideal approach (FGD1 6-3.1).

Pair modular teaching with other modalities (FGD1 6-3.2).

3. Empowering for Alternative Learning Modality. The theme is driven by the narratives given by the informants that described their aspiration for the better implementation of the learning modules through capacity building and mentoring. Informants during the one-on-one interview narrated and said:

I attended webinars on how to deliver education using this type of modality, the modular distance teaching modality but the application is quite different (IDI 3-2.1).

Teachers should be trained effectively on how to deliver this type of modality (IDI 3-3).

Attend series of DepEd webinars that can help me gain new knowledge to cope up the new normal set-up (IDI 6-3).

Informants 1 and 8 during the FGD also added:

There should be at least one day in a week allocated for mentoring of students to clarify confusions, give instructions, and answer queries from the students. Technical assistance, trainings and seminars, should be provided to teachers (FGDI 1-3.2).

Teachers should be given the opportunity to attend seminars and workshops to improve their skills in delivering lessons in this type of modality. Prior to the implementation, we attended webinars, but I believe this was insufficient (FGD1 8-3).

4. Innovating Quality Amidst Flexibility. The theme is driven by the narratives shared by informants during the interview describing their aspiration to create innovations to make the teaching and learning process in this pandemic effective.

Informants during the individual interview shared and said:

Aside from teachers' seminars, modules should be error-free. Quality education is synonymous with error-free learning material. Limit or minimize the number of pages and activities in every module in all subject areas. (IDI 3-3.2).

All school teachers have autonomy and freedom to design their own modules. The modules, however, must be evaluated for quality assurance, and progress will be tracked and monitored (IDI 7-3).

We are all aware that errors are unavoidable at times. Teachers should reassess the modules and ensure that all learning activities are appropriate for the learners' needs (IDI 7-3.2).

Also, informants during the FGD shared same sentiments and said:

The content of the modules. It should be error-free (FGDI 3-3.1).

Limit the number of activities which some are already a duplication (FGDI 4-3).

The content of the modules should double check by the curriculum specialists (FGDI 5-3).

Modules that are free of errors and have been quality-assured by curriculum experts (FGD1 7-3).

Less activities for the students (FGD1 7-3).

Keep the activities in the modules to a minimum because it will be too much for the students (FGD1 7-3.2)

Minimize the activities in the modules because it will be a burden for the students (FGD1 8-3.2).

5. Modules with a Heart for Learners' Well-being. This theme was driven by the narratives shared by the informants describing their sentiments on the continual improvement of the modules, especially on the aspect of further polishing the modules, simplifying the content, and those that are error-free.

The informants from the individual interview said:

Yes of course, because the modular teaching modality is not perfect or even close to perfection. First, the curriculum itself, though the competencies have been lessened still we have a lot of competencies to be covered. I think DepEd shall look into this. Second, the learning activities to be answered or completed are too many. Students complain about this and they don't find it healthy and just for them. The activities are intended for everybody not considering the level of interest and knowledge of the students (IDI 4-3.1).

I aspire to an error-free module in a book-type format same with the private schools one modular textbook only every quarter. I believe we can reduce the cost of the printing if we can have this one. Also, reduce the activities in the module. Students are not happy with so many activities anymore. They are stressed out on this (IDI 5-3).

For me the modules alone, some content had a grammar error, blurry pic and the likes and it should be improved in order not to create any confusion on the part of the learner (IDI 6-3.2).

The contents of the modules must be simplified, and teachers must simplify the lessons. The teachers shall provide more examples. For easy description and identification of students, do not use black ink if the photo needs to be printed in color (IDI 7-3.1).

Module in a book style or format and with lesser activities but still adheres to the standards (IDI 8-3).

The content of the modules should be improved. There are so many activities that learners do not understand and difficult for them to answer (IDI 8-3.1).

The content of the modules should be improved. The DepEd should prepare books because printing of modules takes time and additional workload for teachers (IDI 8-3.2).

This was further supported by the informants from the FGD, describing the aspiration on the further development of the modules. They said:

One of these is on the materials necessary for the production of modules. Another is in terms of content of the modules. The content should be reduced to avoid wastage of resources without sacrificing the skills that the students should learn (FGDI 1-3.1).

Modules that are really suited to the needs of the individual learners for some of the activities are too complex and hard for the slow learners to comprehend (FGDI 7-3).

The content of the modules should be limited but is aligned with the standards. Avoid duplication of activities (FGDI 8-3).

6.Focusing Further on the Essential. The theme is driven by the researcher from the narratives shared by the informants describing their aspirations to improve the focus of modular learning which is to continue learning and to ensure that learners are learning. Informants from the FGD shared their aspirations on this aspect. They said:

I aspire for more organize process in printing and distribution of modules, and availability of resources to maximize time (FGDI 1-3).

DepEd shall limit the clerical works to teachers so that they can give more time and attention to teaching and learning and improving themselves so that they can really provide quality education to the learners (FGDI 4-3).

Provide a unified Self-learning module and no more printing anymore for it takes time to prepare the modules. Instead of focusing on the learners, monitoring, our time is already focused on the printing alone (FGDI 4-3.2).

A sort of modular textbook ready for distribution and the teacher will just distribute it. No need to print anymore volumes of pages and copies (FGDI 7-3).

Limit clerical works for teachers to have more time in the preparation and delivery of modular instruction (FGDI 7-3.2).

Limit clerical works for teachers to have more time in the preparation and delivery of modular instruction (FGDI 7-3.2).

Modules will be converted into modular textbooks, and I'll be able to distribute them as soon as I get them. Printing is no longer a chore. The days and time spent printing the module will be used in monitoring, home visits, and tutoring as a result (FGDI 8-3).

7.Flexing the Curriculum for Quality Education. The theme is driven by the researcher from the narratives shared by the informants describing their aspiration for changing or flexing the curriculum for the quality of education in this time of the pandemic.

Some of the MELC Competencies shall not be included because some competencies duplicate from other competencies and it is no longer necessary (IDI 6-3.1).

Curriculum decongestion (FGDI 4-3.1).

DISCUSSION

As presented by Shosha (2012), Colaizzi's phenomenological data analysis approach revealed an active strategy for achieving the depiction of those people's life experiences. It entails deciphering the data and determining key assertions, which are then translated into formed meanings. Following that, groupings of topic clusters were created to form the final thematic construct.

To accomplish each method effectively, several tactics and strategies were used to ensure the research outcomes were trustworthy. The correct implementation of Colaizzi's descriptive phenomenology approach would produce a comprehensive account of the corpus of knowledge about human experience, and hence would be a successful technique for laying the groundwork for future study (Shosha, 2012).

This case study that explored the different experiences and aspirations of the selected Junior High School teachers of Catbalogan City Division in Modular Distance Teaching Modality is anchored on the Transactional Distance Theory by Michael Moore (1997), Constructivist Theory by John Dewey (1938), and the Theory of Distance Education by Borje Holmberg (1995).

The main theory used was the Transactional Distance Theory of Michael Moore (1997). The idea distinguishes physical or temporal distance between learners and teachers during a transaction between them. Three elements must be considered while developing transactions between professors and students in distance learning. One is conversation, another is its structure and the learner's autonomy as the third element. This theory assumes that distance learning is considered "transactional" if these three elements are present.

The constructivist theory of John Dewey (1938) is also a supporting theory of this research endeavor. John Dewey's Constructivist theory of education can be adapted to apply to the museum setting. The concepts are in line with our current understandings of learning

and knowledge, yet they are in opposition to traditional museum operations. In order to apply these ideas to our work, we must reflect on our own practices.

In this theory, what is being presented in the classroom makes a difference from what is encountered by every learner in day-to-day activities. That is why he would always speak of making teachers expert learners who can guide students into adapting cognitive strategies highlighting self-testing, articulating and understanding, asking probing questions, and reflection.

This study was also supported by the Theory of Distance Education of Borje Holmberg (1995), which focuses on how distance affects learning and how distance professors should engage with students. Borje Holmberg coined the Guided Didactic Communication, which can be done in two ways: one-sided Simulated Conversations or two-sided Real Conversation.

In essence, Holmberg believes that fostering empathy between learning and tutoring parties through appropriate one- and two-way interactions motivates and encourages students to engage personally in their studies. "True learning is essentially an individual activity that can only be completed via an internalization process," it also implies. This is a reasonable assumption to make in favor of the concept of distance education.

Other related studies were also cited to support the findings of this study. Shown below are the emergent themes derived from the responses of the informants based on the sub-problems of the study.

I. Positive and Negative Experiences in Modular Teaching Modality

A. Positive Experiences the Informants Encountered in Modular Teaching Modality

This overarching theme depicts the sub-problem of the study what are the positive and negative experiences of the informants encountered in modular distance teaching modality. From the responses of the key informants, there are twelve (12) emergent themes were generated. There are five (5) emergent themes for the positive experiences encountered by the informants in the modular distance teaching modality and seven (7) emergent themes for the negative experiences encountered by the informants in the modular distance teaching modality. The emergent themes for the positive experiences encountered by the informants in the modular distance teaching modality are as follows:

1. Teaching with a Heart. The theme that was developed from the phenomenological narratives expressed by the informants leads to a deeper meaning of teaching in this modular distance learning modality, giving a chance to know learners better.

The informants' responses revealed that teachers prepare materials for self-paced learning that motivate both the academic and mental aspects of learners. They provide hands-on monitoring and innovative learning. Face-to-face monitoring allows them to gain a deeper understanding of the learners' and students' life. They also develop

resourcefulness in the preparation of learning modules. They imply innovation to ensure that learners receive quality education.

This emergent theme is greatly supported by the theory of Distance Education by Holmberg, which emphasizes that there is a big impact of distance education where the teachers must communicate with students to ensure real learning in the implementation of self-paced learning materials.

This was further supported by the study of Baysinger (2020), who mentioned that experts can devise tutorials even though they are in different institutions. Relatively, Willmot and Perkin (2016) highlight that the makers of modules experienced a good relationship with their students compared to before.

2.Learning Independently. The said theme is derived from the responses of the informants describing the effect of modular learning among learners, which can be considered a good sign for the process of learning.

The informants' responses tell us that students generate creative outputs with minimum supervision, develop independent learning submit outputs on time, and learn at their own pace at home.

This is well supported by the Constructivist Theory of John Dewey which emphasizes that education should be based on real-life experiences. In addition, Sejpal (2013) sees that modules enable learners to have control over their learning and accept greater responsibility for learning. This was also supported by Nadas and Vidal (2018) when they mentioned that modularization gives learners the chance to choose an appropriate learning approach and gives learners the chance to reset a unit rather than repeat the whole process of assessment. Also, Clover (2017) identifies that modular instruction gives the utmost convenience, which teaches learners to be independent learners.

3.Developing Family Link. The theme is derived from the responses of the informants expressing how the learning modules developed the link between family members at most are parents making time to teach their children.

This is supported greatly by the theory of Constructivism of John Dewey which highlights those students participating in real-world scenarios also could demonstrate their knowledge via creativity and teamwork.

It also reflects the study of Nadas and Vidal (2018) where they highlight those modules give a link between family and peers to prepare students for the future phase of their education.

4.Healthy Teaching. The theme that has been developed comes from the phenomenological narratives expressed by the informants, expressing how light the process of teaching and learning is today in this pandemic because there are informants who see it as an avenue to stay healthy amidst the pandemic.

This theme clustered is in line with the theory of Transactional Distance Theory of Moore (1997) which speaks of the second factor giving emphasis on the structure, specifically on the course's ability to accommodate individual students' needs which is part of the development of the learning modules.

Moreover, Hilmi et al. (2016) highlighted in their study that those teachers who were satisfied with the hygiene factors which include the relationship with the administration or supervisor, with their colleagues, pay factor, or salary, and also their satisfaction in terms of the motivation factor on both the fulfillment of the hygiene and motivation factors towards their job satisfaction.

5.Motivated and Inspired. The theme generated from the phenomenological narratives expressed by the informants expresses the brighter side of the pandemic where even if modular learning is quite demanding, they can find the light of motivation and inspiration along with the modular distance teaching modality.

This is supported by the Theory of Distance Education by Holmberg (Seville, 2019) which emphasizes that learners and teachers are motivated and encouraged to participate personally in the teaching and learning process through developing empathy between learning and tutoring parties through proper one- and two-way exchanges.

It was also supported by Wilmot and Perkin (2016) who found in their study that the makers of modules experienced a good relationship with their students compared to before.

B. Negative Experiences the Informants Encountered in Modular Teaching Modality

1. Deteriorating Motivation for Learning. The theme that was generated from the narrative given by the informants expressed the opposite of the light of motivation and inspiration because some informants have deteriorating motivation for learning due to the other side of the modular distance teaching modality.

The informants are disappointed with the unanswered activities in the module, a comprehension issue that leads to non-submission of outputs, exhaustion in the preparation of modules with a large number of students, and the modules submitted are incomplete in terms of activities.

This emergent theme is supported by the Theory of Distance Education formulated by Holmberg when he highlighted that another pervasive characteristic of distance education is the sense of personal connection between the teaching and learning parties that encourages enjoyment and motivation in the classroom. This is further supported by the study of Fox (2020) when she mentioned that strong motivation is required in the implementation of distance education.

2. Unprogressive Result for Learning. The theme was derived from the narratives of the informants expressing their frustration relative to the negative effect of the modular

distance teaching modality on the progress of students' learning in this pandemic. The informants revealed that modules in Math, Science, and English are not comprehensible, learners with intellectual capacity and no parental guidance and supervision cannot catch up with the activities, and learners lack the fundamental skills needed for learning the subject.

This is greatly supported by the Theory of Distance Education of Holmberg (Seville, 2019) which gives emphasis on the achievement of such goals and the implementation of precise study processes and approaches are aided by intellectual enjoyment and study motivation.

This was also supported by the study of Fox (2020) when she identified that in doing modular instruction in a distant learning approach, there is a need for strong motivation which has willpower, responsibility, and self-control.

3. Risk-taking for the Sake of Learning. This theme described the risks made by informants to continue the learning process. The informants revealed that they have to deliver the modules even if the fare is expensive and there is a risk of being infected by the virus. They are also dissatisfied with the lack of adherence to the module distribution schedule. This emergent theme is supported by the Transactional Distance Theory of Moore (1997) which highlights in the second factor that flexibility includes aspects like the extent to which course goals and objectives are pre-determined, the pedagogical model used in teaching the subject, the nature of course assessment, and the course's ability to accommodate individual students' needs.

Furthermore, this is also supported by the study of Kalantzis and Cope (2020) who highlighted that the teacher's task is to commit their learning design to the digital record and take the risk in the delivery of the module.

4. Earning over Learning. The theme generated from the narrative stated by the informants expresses the frustration of informants towards some learners who choose to earn rather than invest in their academic performance.

The informants affirmed that students prioritize work above school, which delays output submissions, there is a lack of learning owing to socioeconomic constraints, and students submit modules late.

This emergent theme is supported by the Theory of Distance Education of Holmberg (Seville, 2019) which highlights that distance education provides an avenue for learners to set a central concept of motivation in every decision made.

Moreover, this theory is also supported by the study of Nadas and Vidal (2018) who added that modularization affected the learning of learners because there will be a creation of danger, destruction, and inconsistency in the learning programs because of the delivery method and assessment practices in the curriculum; and the diversion of priority rather than focusing on learning.

5. Losing Trust among Parents. The theme-driven responses of the informants express another negative aspect seen in the modular learning modality, which is the participation of parents in the academic performance of their children and the demotivation brought about by lack of cooperation.

The informants expressed that some parents are not cooperating with the modular delivery instruction. They do not receive the modules on time. Owing to a lack of time, parents are unable to fully implement effective learning, and parents are unable to teach their children due to a lack of subject expertise.

This emergent theme is supported by the Theory of Distance Education of Holmberg which assumes that distance education involves the participation of stakeholders and parents. As a result, his idea aims to encourage personalized learning.

Moreover, the study by Fox (2020) highlights the need for strong motivation from the stakeholders and parents in order to fully implement the modules and their products. Also, Mak and Georges (2017) added that the satisfactory completion of the self-paced modules depends on having access to parents' guidance.

6. Exhausting Resources for Learning. The theme-driven from the narrative expressed by informants describes another negative impact of modular learning modality on the informants, where they have insufficient materials for the production of modules.

The informants revealed that producing modules consumes more time and personal resources. The lack of resources causes the delay of the module production.

This emergent theme, therefore, is supported by this emergent theme is supported by the Theory of Distance Education of Holmberg (Seville, 2019) which highlights that another characteristic that can be identified for distance education is a well-developed instructional material.

In relation to this, the study of Baysinger (2020) shared that a teacher who would consider in engaging in modular learning should be well-provided with equipment and materials and should be given an emphasis for the use of delivering it properly.

7. Undependable Students Learning. The theme is driven by the narrative responses describing their experiences on the aspect of the learner's learning authenticity and reliability. Furthermore, the originality of students' performance made during this time of pandemic is at stake. Since it's difficult to identify who made the work.

The informants revealed that the assessment is delayed due to late submissions, which causes feedback to be delayed, that the assessment results are unreliable, that there is uncertainty about the performance of the students in terms of their outputs and assessment, that the checking of the modules is difficult due to unanswered parts and doubts about their completion, and that the quality of outputs submitted by the learners is poor and does not meet the standards reflected on the rubric.

This emergent theme is supported by the Constructivist Learning Theory (Miranda, 2012) because it gives emphasis on the opposition to the idea of schools focusing on memorization and offered a technique of directed living which should be done in this pandemic.

This is true when Tedla and Desta (2015) highlight that the modules' ineffective results are because of the students' poor performance. The approach of instruction made in the modules makes students feel the teacher-centered approach. That is why instructors change their way of teaching to more teacher-centered education. In terms of assessment, instructors feel that their students don't grasp the required skill if they administer assessments frequently. Furthermore, it becomes a burden to them every time they assess because it only addresses the students' content understanding and not the skills developed. As an alternative, they suggested an interactive assessment, allowing learners to practice or apply what developed skills are after a module. And lastly, they found out the ineffectively of the module after seeing these problems.

II. Descriptions of the Informants in the Preparation of Modular Teaching Modality

There are four (4) emergent themes under this overarching theme that describe the responses of the key informants to the description of their experiences in the preparation of the learning modules.

1. All Efforts Are Exhausted for Learning. The theme describes the manifested effort done to continue learning despite the challenge of the pandemic. The key informants' direct experiences responded that their experiences in exerting all best efforts to make the teaching and learning effective using the learning modules.

The informants' responses revealed that the preparation of the learning modules is tedious and requires complete materials to avoid delay in the module production and makes the learning process effective in the temporal absence of the teacher.

This description presented by the informants is in consonance with the theory of Distance Education by Holmberg (Seville, 2019) which highlights that it is important that the structure should be clear which is referred to as the pedagogical model or means used for the teaching and learning process. Having mentioned this difficulty experienced by informants in the preparation of the learning modules, Baysinger (2020) affirms that teachers have to do more extensive labor in order to execute modular instruction.

2. Modifying Teaching and Learning Using Modules for Learning. The theme-driven describes the ways made by the informants to modify the teaching and learning with the use of the modules. This also gives an avenue where the informants become the innovator in order to make the teaching and learning process simpler and more understandable as they prepare the learning modules.

This finding supports the theory of Distance Education by Holmberg (Seville, 2019) which says that one of the pervasive characteristics of distance education is that there is well-developed self-instructional material.

This theme of giving an avenue for teachers to become a designer of their modules is supported by the study of the University Association for Contemporary European Studies (2020) which highlight that designing a learning module is a privilege and at the same time a responsibility for they have to develop it with a clear purpose, constructive alignment, and a contextualized course.

3. Demanding Yet Rewarding. The developed theme describes the demands that the modules require which becomes for them a rewarding task. Along the way of the development of learning modules, informants mentioned the challenging tasks of doing modules but seeing the appreciation expressed by parents and learners, the feeling of exhaustion is carefully paid off.

This theme clustered is in line with the theory of Transactional Distance Theory of Moore (1997) which speaks of the second factor giving emphasis on the structure specifically on the course's ability to accommodate individual students' needs which is part of the development of the learning modules.

Moreover, Kalantzis and Cope (2020) highlights that the teacher's task is to commit to their learning design and greatly relevant to the needs of the community which is greatly appreciated by students which becomes a fulfilling part for teachers.

4. Mens Sana in Corpore Sano (A Sound Mind in a Sound Body). The quest for continuous learning in this pandemic has been challenging among the informants that they have to consider their health conditions which will be catering the effectiveness of learning in a way that is structured and planned in a learning condition just like in this pandemic.

This is evident relatively with what the theory of Transactional Distance Theory of Moore (1997) which speaks of the temporal distance that separates learners from the teacher in the transaction between them and is occurring in this structured or planned learning situation.

This was also supported by the study of Fox (2020) when the study conducted identified that the implementation of distance education is an advantage on the part of the teacher for it provides convenience in any unexpected event.

III. Aspirations of the Informants in Improving the Modular Teaching Modality

This overarching theme depicts the sub-problem of the study what are the different aspirations of the teachers towards the implementation of the modular learning modality relative to the responses given by the informants of the study. From the responses of the

key informants, there are seven (7) emergent themes identified by the researcher. They are as follows:

1. The Commitment for Continuous Learning. The theme is driven by the narratives given by the informant describing their commitment to continue learning through the use of learning modules. The informants revealed that providing quality education to learners must continue despite the pandemic as part of the work.

This is consistent and supported by the Transactional Distance Theory of Moore (1997) when he highlights that distance does not mean that learning won't continue because it is just a temporal distance that separates learners from the teacher in the transaction between them and is occurring in the structured or planned learning situation.

This continuation of learning using modules that gives chance for learners to continue learning this pandemic is supported by the study of Dejene and Chen (2019) stating in his study that faculties and teachers have a problem to the point that they violate professional ethics caused by inadequacy of time, preparing modules for bulk or big size of classes.

2. Assurance of Human Interactive Modules. The theme is driven by the narratives given by the informants to describe the need for adjusting the modules for learners to have a sound understanding of the modules where they can interact through the answers expressed in their modules.

The informants revealed that contextualization of module content is required for easy comprehension. There is also a requirement to provide a feedback mechanism that may be used to change the teaching and learning process. To innovate the learning process, live interaction between the teacher and students will be utilized.

This is supported by the Transactional Distance Theory of Moore (1997) which mentions that there is a factor that let learners develop autonomy. They participate in the course the autonomy of the learner is inextricably linked. This can interfere with a learner's feeling of self-direction or self-determination. That is why the need for more humane interactive modules are developed the tendency for autonomy has big chances.

This was also supported by the study of Burge (2019) where it was described that three things should be considered in the preparation of the modules which includes; clarity of the purpose and aspirations of the modules for student participants and communicate these to students. It is essential that in creating a learning module, it is necessary to have clear, achievable goals or outcomes to increase every learner's learning gradually.

3. Empowering for Alternative Learning Modality. The theme is driven by the narrative given by the informants that describe their aspiration to have a better implementation of the learning modules through capacity building and mentoring. The informants revealed that there is a need for upskilling of teachers' talents and skills especially on the conduct of modular distance teaching modality.

This is supported by the Transactional Distance Theory of Moore (1997) under the second factor which is more on the structure which describes the rigidity or flexibility of the course. This factor also includes aspects like the extent to which course goals and objectives are pre-determined, the pedagogical model used in teaching the subject, the nature of course assessment, and the course's ability to accommodate individual students' needs.

This is also supported by the study conducted by Burge (2019) highlighting that the module is constructively aligned, meaning the learners can actively construct their understanding and all necessary alignment with the teaching and assessment with the intended learning outcomes. Therefore, it is necessary to consider the type of course handled, resources available, disciplinary context, and, of course, the national and legal requirements.

4. Innovating Quality Amidst Flexibility. The theme is driven by the narratives shared by informants during the interview describing their aspiration of creating innovations to make the teaching and learning process in this pandemic effective.

The informants agreed that developing a quality assurance framework and identifying content experts is essential. Quality certified modules encourage successful learning. This is supported by the Transactional Distance Theory of Moore (1997) under the third factor which is more on the structure where the learners will be able to develop autonomy. As they participate in the course the autonomy of the learner is inextricably linked. This can interfere with a learner's feeling of self-direction or self-determination.

This is also true in the study of Pappas (2015) when he said that to create perfect learning which caters to the student-centered learning unit and these are the following: there must be an advanced and specified learning objective.

5. Modules with a Heart for Learner's Well-being. This theme was driven by the narratives shared by the informants describing their sentiments on the continual improvement of the modules, especially on the aspect of further polishing the modules, simplifying the content, and that which is error-free.

This is supported by the Theory of Distance Education of Holmberg (Seville, 2019) which highlights that one of the characteristics of Distance Education is that well-developed self-instructional material and two-way dialogue can generate such feelings.

This is further supported by the study of Pappas (2015) when he said that Learners must have feedback; when they made an error in answering scenarios or any question, it is essential to note that they will know how to improve moving forward.

6. Focusing Further on the Essential. The theme is driven by the researcher from the narratives shared by the informants describing their aspiration on changing or flexing the curriculum for the quality of education at this time of the pandemic. The informants stressed the importance of a defined method in module production and that centralized printing is advantageous.

This is supported by the Constructivist theory of Dewey (Lamon, 2020) which highlights that to present it in a clear way, what is being presented in the classroom makes a difference from what is encountered by every learner in day-to-day activities. That is why he would always speak of making teachers an expert learner who can guide students into adapting cognitive strategies highlighting self-testing, articulating and understanding, asking probing questions, and reflection.

This is supported by the study of Acuram (2015) when he mentioned that in Duldulao's Model, it is highlighted that modules should have the things to be known, things that are nice to be known, things that are less nice to be known, things that are barely relevant, and things that might be used someday. Accordingly, the structure and the content are equal, and the arrangement of materials is simple to complex.

7. Flexing the Curriculum for Quality Education. The theme is driven by the researcher from the narratives shared by the informants describing their aspiration on changing or flexing the curriculum for the quality of education this time of the pandemic. The informants highlighted that the curriculum should be revisited as some of the competencies are repeated.

This emergent theme is supported by Theory of Distance Learning by Holmberg (Seville, 2019) that highlight the need the implementation of correct study processes and approaches are aided by intellectual enjoyment and study motivation.

Further, this is supported by the study of Gupta (2017) when it was highlighted also that most of the 21st century learners would always want relevant, mobile, self-paced, and personalized content learning. And this need is fulfilled with the creation of learning modules. Also, Mutiara, Zuhairi and Kurniati (2007), added that in creating a learning module it must be remembered that it serves as a major learning resource for distance learners. The design, development and product of learning materials should carefully consider, the systematic and scientific principles of instructional design. Quality learning materials are very dependent upon consistent implementation of quality assurance principles.

Conclusions

This study explored the experiences of Junior High School Teachers in modular teaching modality, Catbalogan City Division, Catbalogan City, Samar, the School Year 2021-2022: Specifically, the study sought out answers to the following queries:

1. What are the positive and negative experiences of the informants encountered in the modular teaching modality?
2. How would the informants describe their preparation in the modular learning modality?
3. What are the aspirations of informants to improve the modular teaching modality?

This study employed the qualitative research design utilizing the single case-study approach to explore the narratives of junior high school teachers in the modular teaching modality. The study was conducted on all junior high school teachers in the Schools Division of Catbalogan City. Using the inclusion criteria identified by the researcher, sixteen (16) informants were identified to participate in the data gathering. Eight (8) of them participated in the individual interview (IDI). On the other hand, the remaining eight (8) participated in the Focus Group Discussion (FGD). An interview guide was utilized to gather data from the informants. This interview guide was validated by experts to establish the validity of its content. The data was analyzed using the Colaizzi method. Based on the result and findings of the study, three (3) emergent themes were identified. The first emergent theme with twelve (12) subthemes described the experiences of the junior high school in the modular learning modalities; the second emergent theme with four (4) subthemes described the preparation of the learning modules, and the third with seven (7) subthemes described the aspirations of the junior high school teachers on modular teaching modality.

For the positive experiences of the junior high school teachers in the modular teaching modality, the following subthemes were clustered: *Teaching with a Heart, Learning Independently, Developing Family Link, Healthy Teaching, Motivated and Inspired*. For the negative experiences of the junior high school teachers, the following subthemes were clustered: *Deteriorating Motivation for Learning, Unprogressive Result for Learning, Risk-taking for the Sake of Learning, Earning over Learning, Losing Trust Among Parents, Exhausting Resources for Learning, and Reliability of Students Learning*.

For the preparation of the learning modules, the following subthemes emerged: *All Efforts are Exhausted for Learning, Modifying Teaching and Learning Using Modules for Learning, Demanding yet Rewarding, and Mens Sana in Corpore Sano (A Sound Mind in a Sound Body)*.

For the aspirations of the Junior High School Teachers on modular teaching modality, the following subthemes were clustered: *The Commitment to Continuous Learning, Assurance of Humane Interactive Modules, Empowering for Alternative Learning Modality, Innovating Quality Amidst Flexibility, Modules with a Heart for Learners' Well-being, Focusing Further on the Essential, and Flexing the Curriculum for Quality*.

Recommendations

Anchored on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

- 1.Revisiting the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs).** The need for revisiting this is necessary to have a clear content alignment in the modules made. Capacitating teachers with these MELCs is important to further put inputs that would help the content be contextualized for easier understanding and learning among learners. The Department of Education must empower division offices for the successful implementation of the MELCs in their respective places. By doing this, the simplification

of content would be easier given that divisions will have a team of experts who would help in the development and contextualization of learning in this time of crisis.

2. Module development and quality assurance by a team of experts. In the development of the module, content writers and developers must have the necessary skills and knowledge to develop learning modules that would have to consider the mental condition of learners, especially those who are below-average learners. When modules are done, there must be a group of specialists who have to check the alignment of the activities in the module with the assessment, content, teaching, and learning tasks given, and what is in the MELCs.

3.Provision of sufficient supplies and materials for mass production of modules to be used for modular teaching. It is very important that materials are well provided so that the production will not stop. There must be a group in charge to focus on the production of modules so that teachers will have to focus on the follow-up and interventions so that competencies will be achieved despite the pandemic. This is also to free teachers from spending their personal resources on the production of modules. It is important that the group in charge of the production must innovate and build linkages that would help in providing supplies needed for the production of the modules.

4.Minimizing the activities of the modules to cater to other interventions for better retention. The teaching and learning activities in the module should be minimized so that the acquisition of skills among learners will have a spiral progression. Doing a student inventory would help teachers know how to craft modules having great consideration of the findings found from the student inventory and home visitations. The need for professional mentoring and skills-based training is needed by faculty so that the selection of assessment tasks and activities will be trimmed to the most essential activities that will only be added to the modules.

5. SDO, Schools, and districts must provide frequent opportunities for continuing professional development for teachers. Professional development activities should be appropriately supported and accessible to all teachers at all stages of their employment. Continuous education is required of teachers to maintain and develop their knowledge throughout time. Teachers' subject-specific pedagogical knowledge and skills should be developed so that they can provide proper technical assistance to learners and parents. Professional development should emphasize a deep understanding of content and discipline-based methods of inquiry, provide multiple perspectives on students as learners, and develop teachers' subject-specific pedagogical knowledge and skills.

Recommendations for Future Study

The researcher recommends the following research topics for future study:

1. Quantitative and qualitative study on the impact of modular teaching in skills-based subjects.
2. Quantitative study on the evaluation of learning modules on the study habits among learners.

3. Qualitative study on the attitude and perception of teachers on the use of modules in teaching laboratory subjects.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher received authorization from the OIC Schools Division Superintendent to conduct interviews at the respondents' schools and the respondents in the city division. The interview guide questions were validated by panel experts. Moreover, informed consent was given to the participants of the study. The objectives, beneficiaries, and potential risks of the study were explained, and the gathered data was utilized for research purposes. Participants were informed that their involvement was voluntary, and their confidentiality was preserved.

Interview data was kept confidential, with no responses or participant details disclosed without written consent. Confidentiality was maintained through informed consent and a detailed letter. Participants were assigned code numbers and access to identifying information was limited to a select few. Data was disposed of promptly after collection.

The researcher committed to maintaining data confidentiality within legal limits, ensuring that any identifiable information would remain confidential except to protect participants' privacy, rights, and welfare. Published or presented research results would not disclose any respondents' identities. Participation was voluntary, with no penalties or loss of benefits for refusal to participate. Respondents could withdraw consent and discontinue participation without any liability, and their legal rights and claims were not waived by participating in the study.

The study safeguarded data by securely storing all collected information. Only the researcher had access, with hard copies kept in a locked cabinet and digital files on a password-protected Data disposal included shredding hard copies of transcriptions, deleting digital files, and destroying the informed consent forms.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

It is with profound thanks and sincerest appreciation that the author acknowledges her indebtedness to the following people who, in one way or another, assisted her in making this research work a successful reality.

To Dr. Rex T. Argate, her adviser, for his guidance and continued efforts in supervising and encouraging her in the performance of her work and for his devotion in checking her output as well as in making the necessary changes and suggestions in the manuscript and for imparting his knowledge and expertise in this study;

To Dr. Yolanda C. Sayson, the Graduate School Dean and the Chairman of the Dissertation Committee, for her recommendations, assistance, encouragement, and support;

To the members of the Panel of Oral Examinations: Dr. Renato C. Sagayno and Dr. Jose L. Pena, for their constructive criticisms and suggestions;
To Dr. Marilyn B. Siao, the Schools Division Superintendent of the Catbalogan City Division for allowing the researcher to conduct her study;
To the sample schools, school heads, and teachers who served as the potent source of information to come up with the findings of this study;
Likewise, to Karin M. Maceda, Vea Marie M. Quitalig, and Junior High School Teachers of Samar Colleges, Inc., for their encouragement and valuable help and support;
To her parents, Misael and Jocelyn Gadin, whose encouragement served as an inspiration;
To her children, Kate Angelique, Kenn Adrian, and Sophie Jane, and her husband, Elizer, who served as her strength and inspiration in life, and
Above all, to the Divine Assistance and Provision in her academic pursuit.

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